

Understanding the User Needs in the Electric Mobility System: a Survey Study

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ABSTRACT:

Despite their potential for environmental impact reduction, Electric Vehicles (EVs) are still characterized by some peculiarities that make their acceptance by users a critical topic. Within the H2020 RESOLVE (Range of Electric SOLUTIONs for L-category Vehicles) project, the specifications for the early concept design of a new L-category EV was based on a study of vehicle requirements. According to the European Regulation, a wide range of different vehicles are included in the “L-category”, each one being described in detail by the Reg.168/2013/EC “on the approval and market surveillance of two-or three-wheel vehicles and quadricycles. Starting from the lesson learned from literature, a survey was prepared in order to identify the needs and the attitudes of a range of potential users, aiming at understanding their opinion and their propensity to use EVs. The Survey was proposed to open public using media such as social networks, website, project communication channels; relevant actors on the sector were contacted for the promotion of the initiative. The questionnaire included different sections related to person description, mobility needs definition, vehicle expectation and current knowledge on the EVs. As a first target, such approach was aimed to correlate the characteristics of the participants with the mobility needs they described. As a second target, their expectations in terms of performances and overall characteristics were identified. Finally, the analysis of the perception of EVs confirmed that most users are correctly informed about EVs potential, but are still considering range as a limitation.

1 INTRODUCTION

European cities are increasingly congested due to the increased demand and usage of motor vehicles. These vehicles cater to the daily mobility needs of the residents, who mostly use them for commuting. As these vehicles become more numerous, emissions increase, parking gets scarcer, and noise levels affect the quality of life and health of city-dwellers. Moreover, the reduction of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions and the expansion of

renewable energies are crucial challenges for the future. Cars are responsible for around 12% of total EU GHG emissions. The 2015 and 2021 EC targets represent reductions of 18% and 40% respectively compared with the 2007 fleet average of 158.7g/km of CO₂ [3].

2 EV: NEW VEHICLES FOR OLD DRIVERS

Such relevant emission reduction requires considerable restructuring in all sectors of the energy system. One of the main concern at this aim is the application of alternative propulsion systems. Pure electric powered transport holds the greatest potential for GHG emissions reductions, since the electricity can be produced from essentially carbon-neutral sources. Nevertheless, the EU is working to introduce electric vehicles beyond 2020, improving technology over time and developing the recharging infrastructure [2]. Even if the most feasible alternatives to traditional Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles (ICEVs) is represented by EVs, the rate of adoption of these vehicles is not high enough to have a significant impact on emissions and on urban living conditions [5]. This is because EVs are unable to compete with ICEVs especially due to low range achievable and high cost. According to a study on the topic [8], the *limited instrumental attributes of EVs* (e.g. low range) influence the overall judgement in terms of *less joy and pleasure in owning and driving an EV and a negative social identity*. It has been shown that these effects are largely dependent on how an Electric Mobility System (EMS) is set up as well as how it is used [4]. Adopting the perspective of human centered systems engineering three essential components should be taken into account when optimizing user-system interaction: technical system, user and task [4]. In this paper we will focus on the user, investigating the elements that make EV and EMS a feasible alternative to ICE and to traditional transport system. EVs driver copes with a range of new and unfamiliar technologies and it will be vital for automotive manufacturers to make the driver's interaction experience positive and rewarding [9]. EV Drivers will encounter completely new concepts such as range management, charging procedures, recharging duration, very low noise, strong acceleration and limited space etc. [1], in addition to unfamiliar issues such as novel start

and stopping procedures and the effect that driving style has on the potential mileage range [9]. The driver should understand how to utilize the EV's special driving qualities and should be supported in developing trust and understanding which factors affect the available range, in order to be able to reduce concerns and range anxiety [6] (i.e. tips on the proper use of the regenerative braking) [9]. Although EV field trials have a long-standing tradition, there is very little published research about how to design an EV dashboard in order to overcome these issues.

3 USERS' ACCEPTANCE OF EVS: A SURVEY ON POTENTIAL USERS

The history of EVs demonstrates that many obstacles – related to cost, to range and to charging infrastructure – have been limiting their diffusion. However, recent analysis on mobility needs demonstrated EVs potential. Since little data are available about Electric L-vehicles (powered two-three wheelers and quadricycles), a survey was lead within RESOLVE project. RESOLVE (Range of Electric SOLUTIONs for L-category Vehicles) is an H2020 EU funded project (more details at <http://www.resolve-project.eu/>).

3.1 Scopes of the survey

According to a recent survey on potential EV users [8] vehicle purchase attitude is associated to three main categories of attributes: instrumental (functionality or utility provided – e.g. cost, performance), hedonic (emotional experience derived from use - joy, pleasure), symbolic (self or social identity related to the possession). The survey presented for the RESOLVE project was primarily aimed to assess the instrumental needs of the users in relation to EVs in general, and to L-category vehicles in particular. During the study, users' current knowledge and opinion were explored too. The survey was structured in 4 sections: 1. Person description; 2. Vehicle ownership and mobility needs; 3. Extended description of mobility needs; 4. Opinion on EVs.

3.1.1 Panel description

About 800 responses (20% in Italian and 80% in English) were collected. The identification of users' nationality showed that Italian users were predominant, but that also at least a 5% of share represented Great Britain, Austria, Germany, Poland and France. The age of the population was varied, being mostly represented by 25 to 64 years old users.

3.1.2 Transport habits and mobility needs

This part was aimed at understanding which transport modes are currently used by participants, based on the area where she/he lives. A crucial question to identify user needs was about the typical driving habitude. As demonstrated by former research [7], the needs can significantly vary between week and weekend days. Figure 1 shows that the most part of users (about 90%) declared that a distance below 60 km is usually driven for almost every weekday, while longer distances are driven on weekend days. Urban roads are the most frequently driven in weekdays; mixed patterns including rural roads and motorways are typical of weekend use. Both data, even if coming from self-estimation, are in line with researches based on trip diaries and GPS measurements [7] **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** The distance driven and ridden in a year shows that about 60% of total users are included within a value of 15000 km/year.

Figure 1 – Daily distance traveled by the users (self-estimation)

Most users are strongly sensitive on the transport-related issues; most of them (90%) are worried about “air pollution” and “noise pollution”. Traffic congestion, parking needs and mobility costs are mostly identified as critical issues. Regarding restricted traffic and pedestrian zones, the panel under study was divided: about 50% considered the accessibility to those zones as

a potential issue.

3.1.3 Extended description of mobility needs

This section was aimed to collect the direct opinion of the users about their needs and their expectations on EVs. The user was asked to rank a number of options about the features desired for a hypothetical innovative vehicle. Table 1 shows that such vehicle is perceived to be a mean of transportation for everyday use rather than for fun. Many positions in fact included the desire to transport a passenger and a certain amount of goods, to reduce the cost of fuel, to improve urban usability. Each row represents a rank level; columns show the three most chosen answers. A direct question about range was provided too: about 65% of the users would be satisfied with a range below 120km, which is compatible with the performances of current EVs. Charging could be feasible in home position (55%), while lower percentages were evaluated for workplace (35%).

Table 1 - Results to the question "In case of using/buying a new vehicle for personal mobility, it is relevant to me..."

Rank	1 st choice	2 nd choice	3 rd choice
1	Transport more than one passenger	Reduce the risk of being stuck in traffic	Reduce the cost of fuel
2	Transport a certain amount of goods	Park easily	Transport more than one passenger
3	Full protection from weather	Transport a certain amount of goods	Park easily
4	Possibility to drive it in cold winters	Access to motorways	Transport a certain amount of goods
5	Access to motorways	Transport a certain amount of goods	Full protection from weather

3.1.4 Opinion on electric vehicles

Looking at Figure 1, the positive qualities of EVs are known by the most part of users, which are also recognizing attributes like easiness to drive and comfort. About 19% disagree about environmental friendliness (a characteristic which, effectively, partially depends on the context of use) and the most part of users identify the range as a critical factor. Table 1 clearly

shows that the main motivation for the use of EV is currently declared to be the costs, the efficiency and the environmental aspect.

Figure 4 – Responses to “Do you agree/disagree that driving an EV gives you the following benefits in comparison with ICEVs?”

Table 2 – Extract from the results for the question “Please rank main reasons to use or buy an EV”

Rank level	1 st choice	2 nd choice	3 rd choice
1	Fuel cost	Environmental impact reduction	Efficiency
2	Fuel cost	Cost of ownership	Efficiency
3	Cost of ownership	Efficiency	Fuel cost
4	Efficiency	Cost of ownership	Driving pleasure
5	Driving pleasure	Comfort	Access restricted traffic areas

4 CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, the study is significantly coherent with former literature experiences, demonstrating that for urban use most users agree on the usability of electric vehicles, but they also require an higher range. Considering that PTWs (Powered Two Wheelers) are perceived as “fun” vehicles, the panel highlighted a strong attention on aspect such as: i) Cost; ii) Safety; iii) Transport capabilities (passenger, bag); iv) Urban usability and parking; v) Comfort; vi) Weather protection, in order to get a vehicle suitable for general purpose use. The panel under study due to the former experiences and the high average level of study is probably representative of a quite advanced and informed user, if compared with common driver.

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